

An Event Driven Campus Navigation System On Android Platform

Akshay S. Pagare, Hitesh O. Pal, Sachin A. Patil and Varsha M. More
Department of Computer Engineering,
L.G.N.Sapkal College Of Engineering,
Nashik, Maharashtra,
India.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the event based campus navigation system that we are build an android application which helps to candidates/persons to navigate to an event which is being organised in a campus. This application is developed for all the colleges to enter their event details or college workshops or gatherings dates, timings and fees so that it can be viewable to all the students of different colleges and becomes an easy way to participate through this application. There is no such system to inform all existing as well as outside students, teachers and staff to inform about any event very quickly with its proper place, which may start few minutes or few hours later and the structure of fees. As a result there is a high opportunity to miss any valuable event. To reduce this pain inside a university campus, a very user friendly Google map based Event-driven campus navigation system on android platform has been designed, implemented and tested successfully in this work. This application provides route guide for users from his/her own location to desired location and event updates with its proper place.

Keywords: Digital Campus, GPS, Geographical Information System, Human-Centered Computing, Location-Based services, Navigation, Information system.

I. INTRODUCTION

In event based campus navigation system we are actually trying to build a system which helps us to navigate to an event which is being organized in a campus. This system works on a principle basis on android platform and virtual cloud computing. An event based campus navigation system also works on an idea of using web panel. The user in such a system can register for the event online basis. The registered users get the notification related to the event. Once they get the registration details they can take the decision and the system will help them to navigate to the system. The system works with a lot of accuracy and helps users to reach the exact location. Information events are held throughout the year and are a great way to find out where our favourite will be conducted in which college and peoples can participate and we are also provide facility by mobile application .we are developing web site for college admin and system admin and also application for mobile user. Mobile phones are now adays far more than merely

communication devices. In this college can also show his event list to student. we are implementing three user Admin, System and mobile client .and we are use java technology and android.

II. GOALS AND OBJECTIVES

In recent years with the help Google maps, location searching becomes a new trend when people are not aware of their location. Google maps provide lots functionalities like showing any location, alternative path from any location to other location and estimates time to reach the location. But it is not well developed or so much helpful for college campuses. At time of any event in some other college then we face many problem regarding navigation. There is also less chances to know about other college event. Also sometime there may be change in event location, time, etc. Department, library, canteen may change its locations. It is very painful both for existing students, teachers, staffs and new comers. familiar face of her mother are equally essential to existence, development, and growth. To reduce this pain inside university campuses, a very user friendly Google ma based Event driven campus navigation system on android platform has been designed, implemented and tested successfully in this work. This application provides route guide for users from his/her own location to desired location and event updates with its proper place.

III. METHODOLOGY

A systems development life cycle is composed of a number of clearly de_fined and distinct work phases which are used by systems engineers and systems developers to plan for, design, build, test, and deliver information systems. Like anything that is manufactured on an assembly line, an SDLC aims to produce high quality systems that meet or exceed customer expectations, based on customer requirements, by delivering systems which move through each clearly defined phase, within scheduled time-frames and cost estimates. Computer systems are complex and often (especially with the recent rise of service-oriented architecture) link multiple traditional systems potentially supplied by different software vendors. To manage this level of complexity, a number of SDLC models or methodologies have been created, such as waterfall spiral Agile software development rapid prototyping incremental and synchronize and stabilize. The system development life cycle framework provides a sequence of activities for system designers and developers to follow. It consists of a set of steps or phases in which each phase of the SDLC uses the results of the previous one. The SDLC adheres to important phases that are essential for developers, such as planning, analysis, design, and implementation, and are explained in the section below. It includes evaluation of present system, information gathering, feasibility study and request approval. A number of SDLC models have been created: waterfall, fountain, spiral, build and rapid prototyping, incremental, and synchronize and stabilize.

IV . HARDWARE REQUIREMRNTS

No extra hardware interfaces are needed. The system will use the standard hardware and data communications resources provided.

1. Processor Pentium IV Remark Required

2. Hard Disk 40GB Remark Required
3. Android Mobile 1GB RAM Remark Required
4. RAM 512MB Remark Required
5. Keyboard QWERTY Remark Required

V. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT

1. Operating system : Android OS
2. Google MAP API v2

VI. ARCHITECTURE

VII. OUTCOME

The proposed event based campus navigation guidance and updated event information alert system will work on GPS based android mobile. We have to implement the system for campus of college which is a large place. As GPS works very accurately in large range so we have chosen GPS technology for location tracking. It can be used by existing college students, faculty members, and staff and also by parents, visitors. Google Map API v2 has been taken as a template to show campus map. Map option is provided to see event details on map. It is easy for user to access Google map than other navigation system. We can zoom out and zoom in the map. Admin can update event list and details on Admin panel. User can see all event details updated by admin. User can also see the location of event from user current location on GMAP.

VIII. SUMMARY

The Event based campus navigation system takes user input as queries and then provides the solution to the user in the form of location tracking. In the system the relevant mathematical model is used the system uses software like xamp, eclipse ide, etc

IX. CONCLUSION

The Event based campus navigation system is very dynamic and useful system in todays environment. As the world is becoming more and more smart, this system makes our lives smart in an unknown environment. This system really helps the user to track the event register for the event register for the event and get real-time update of the event. This system is going to be very useful in big campuses which would help users to focus on actual event.

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